

Beyond the Moratorium: From Protection to Restoration of *Pterocarpus erinaceus* Poir in Togo

Ayiga E., Segla K.N., Adjonou K., Kokutse A.D., and Kokou K (2026)

Laboratoire de Recherche Forestière, Faculté des Sciences, Université de Lomé, 01BP : 1515, Lomé, Togo
Corresponding author : esseayiga@gmail.com

Summary

As Togo's 10-year moratorium on *Pterocarpus erinaceus* approaches its expiration in 2026, urgent restoration and propagation actions are needed to avoid renewed degradation of this strategic species. *P. erinaceus* is one of the most economically and ecologically valuable tree species in Togo and West Africa, yet its natural populations remain severely threatened by overexploitation and weak natural regeneration. Research conducted in Togo demonstrates that air layering is an effective vegetative propagation technique capable of producing vigorous and resilient planting material for restoration programs.

Plants produced through air layering showed high rooting success, rapid post-transplant recovery, vigorous growth, and low mortality compared with seed-derived seedlings. Despite the urgency of restoring the species, local producers, nurseries, and communities remain insufficiently trained and equipped in practical propagation techniques for large-scale production. Immediate investment in restoration capacity, nursery development, and technical training is therefore essential to support sustainable restoration and domestication efforts for *P. erinaceus* in the post-moratorium period.

Key messages

- 01. The 10-year moratorium on *Pterocarpus erinaceus* approaches its expiration in 2026**
- 02. Restoration capacity remains insufficient**
- 03. Weak nursery systems**
- 04. Local producers, nurseries, and communities remain insufficiently trained and equipped in practical propagation techniques for large-scale production**
- 05. Risk of renewed exploitation pressure**

Immediate investment in restoration capacity, nursery development, and technical training is essential to avoid renewed degradation of *P. erinaceus* populations after the expiration of the moratorium.

This policy brief targets:

forest policy makers; restoration programs; forestry services; NGOs; nursery operators; development partners.

Zoom on uses and Economic Importance (Figure 1)

Pterocarpus erinaceus represents a strategic economic resource for Togo and West Africa. The species supports multiple value chains, including timber production, fuel wood and charcoal supply, livestock feeding, traditional medicine, artisanal products, and rural livelihoods.

Its high-quality wood is widely sought after for furniture making and regional trade, generating significant economic value for local communities and national markets.

Strengthening restoration and sustainable production systems for the species could therefore contribute not only to biodiversity conservation, but also to employment creation, rural income diversification, energy security, and climate-resilient development.

Figure 1: Illustrative uses and threats to *P. erinaceus*. 1: Logging, illegal logging; 2: Loading logs; 3: fuel wood and charcoal supply; 4: Planks for making high-quality furniture; 5: Craft production; 6: Livestock feeding and traditional medicine

Evidence from Research in Togo

Field and nursery experiments conducted in the Togodo Wildlife Reserve and the Zogbépimé forest station evaluated the performance of vegetative propagation through air layering under contrasting seasonal conditions (Photos 2 (A, B, C)).

Photo 2: Stages of layering *P. erinaceus* in situ at the Togodo Protected Area (A: sapwood exposed; B: sapwood covered with potting soil), followed by ex situ transplantation to Zogbépimé, at the experimental site of the UL Forest Research Laboratory

Evidence from Research in Togo

High rooting success through air layering (Table 1)

- Rooting success reached: 70% during the rainy season; 57% during the dry season.
- Stump-origin shoots performed substantially better than shoots collected from mature seed-origin trees.
- Rainy-season propagation produced more vigorous shoots and better establishment.

Table 1: Rooting and growth performance of air layers of *P. erinaceus*

Origin of layering material	Season	Rooted layers (n)	Rooting rate (%)	Layers with callus formation (n)	Dead layers (n)	Mortality rate (%)	Total layers (n)
Stump shoots (ARS)	Dry season	16	57.0	29	34	43.0	79
Stump shoots (ARS)	Rainy season	85	70.0	8	40	30.0	133

Strong survival and growth performance (Table 2; Figs 1, 2; Photos 2,3)

- Transplanted layered plants showed:
 - 90% recovery within two weeks after transplantation;
 - only 5% mortality after four years of monitoring.
 - vigorous shoot development;
 - improved resilience to drought stress.
- In contrast, seed-derived seedlings experienced approximately 80% decline during the same period.
- Layered plants demonstrated:
 - sustained radial growth;

Flexibility of propagation material

The study found no significant differences in growth performance among: apical layers; median layers; proximal layers.

This provides operational flexibility for nursery production and scaling-up activities.

Table 2: Growth parameters of layering shoots

Parameter	Minimum value	Maximum value	Mean ± SD
Basal diameter (mm)	39	92	45.6 ± 9.3
Diameter below first branch (mm)	21.8	77	36.7 ± 10.0
Primary branch diameter (mm)	12	49	23.8 ± 8.1
Total height (m)	1.43	4.15	2.4 ± 0.5
Number of primary branches	2	6	3.7 ± 1.2

Evidence from Research in Togo

Figure 1: Diameter classes of air-layered plants

Figure 2: Height classes of air-layered plants

Photo 2. Field measurement of growth parameters in *Pterocarpus erinaceus* plants established from air-layered propagules at the Zogbépimé experimental station, Togo.

Limitations of conventional cuttings (Photos 4, 5)

Although cuttings formed callus tissue after soaking treatments, root development remained weak and inconsistent, making this technique less reliable under current conditions.

Photo 3. Vegetative development of shoots produced from air-layered branches of *Pterocarpus erinaceus* under field conditions

Photo 5: Delayed rooting (9 months) of two types of cuttings (straight and cross-cut) of *P. erinaceus*

Photo 4: Scar tissue at the base of *P. erinaceus* cuttings soaked in water

Policy Implications

The findings demonstrate that Togo now possesses practical technical knowledge capable of supporting large-scale restoration of *P. erinaceus*. However, this scientific progress has not yet been sufficiently translated into operational restoration programs or community-based production systems. The approaching end of the moratorium represents a major policy turning point:

- protection measures alone will not ensure long-term conservation;
- Restoration and domestication must become national priorities.

The country must therefore move: from protection to restoration.

Priority Actions for Decision-Makers

- 01. Develop a national restoration strategy for *P. erinaceus***
Integrate the species into:
national reforestation programs; climate adaptation strategies; AFR100 restoration commitments; Great Green Wall initiatives.
- 02. Scale up vegetative propagation programs**
Support:
air layering nurseries; clonal multiplication systems; community-based plant production
- 03. Train local producers and forestry technicians**
Establish practical training programs on:
air layering techniques; nursery management; plantation establishment; post-transplant management.
- 04. Promote restoration using stump-origin material**
Encourage the identification and management of exploited stumps as propagation sources due to their superior rooting performance.
- 05. Strengthen research-extension-policy linkages**
Improve collaboration among:
universities; forestry services; local communities; NGOs; restoration projects.

Strategic Opportunity for Togo

The expiration of the 2016 moratorium should not mark a return to exploitation without preparation. Instead, it offers an opportunity to:

- **rebuild degraded populations;** - **strengthen restoration capacity;** - **create sustainable timber resources;** - **support rural livelihoods;** - **improve climate resilience**

Scientific evidence now confirms that effective propagation of *P. erinaceus* is feasible. The priority challenge is therefore no longer whether restoration is possible, but how rapidly restoration efforts can be scaled up nationally.

Conclusion

The future of *Pterocarpus erinaceus* in Togo depends on an urgent transition from passive conservation toward active restoration and domestication. Air layering provides a practical and effective solution for producing resilient planting material capable of supporting large-scale restoration programs.

As the national moratorium approaches its expiration, immediate investments in propagation capacity, nursery systems, technical training, and community-based restoration are essential to secure the long-term sustainability of this strategic species and the ecosystems and livelihoods that depend on it.